

Real-Time sEMG Processing with Spiking Neural Networks on a Low-Power 5K-LUT FPGA

Matteo Antonio Scrugli, Gianluca Leone, Paola Busia, Luigi Raffo, and Paolo Meloni

Abstract—The accurate modeling of hand movement based on the analysis of surface electromyographic (sEMG) signals offers exciting opportunities for the development of complex prosthetic devices and human-machine interfaces, moving from discrete gesture recognition, towards continuous movement tracking.

In this study, we present two solutions for real-time sEMG processing, based on lightweight Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) and efficiently implemented on a Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA, especially suitable for low-power applications. We first assess the performance in the discrete finger gesture recognition task, considering as a reference the NinaPro DB5 dataset, and demonstrating an accuracy of 83.17% in the classification of twelve different finger gestures. We also consider the more challenging problem of continuous finger force modeling, referencing the Hyser dataset for finger tracking during independent extension and contraction exercises. The assessment reveals a correlation of up to 0.875 with the ground-truth forces.

Our systems take advantage of SNNs' inherent efficiency and, dissipating 11.31 mW in active mode, consume 44.6 μ J for a gesture recognition classification and 1.19 μ J for a force modeling inference. Considering dynamic power-consumption management and the introduction of idle periods, average power drops to 1.84 mW and 3.69 mW for these respective tasks.

Index Terms—Spiking Neural Networks, Real-time monitoring, Healthcare.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of effective advanced human-machine interfaces involves the processing and interpretation of a significant amount of complex data collections, encouraging resorting to Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions, based on the continuous advancements demonstrated in increasingly challenging tasks. In this context, real-time prosthetic control based on surface electromyographic signal analysis (sEMG) is of increasing interest [1]. This complex objective has been interpreted as a multi-layered problem, involving as first steps a high-level pattern recognition task for the identification of discrete gestures, and a more demanding continuous regression task for the tracking of the intended movement [2].

Both these approaches rely on continuous real-time monitoring of the sEMG through wearable/embedded systems, thus requiring a processing model able to satisfy the accuracy requirements of this challenging application within stringent resource limitations. Given their inherently efficient event-based nature, Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) have emerged

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as a promising solution. As a consequence, a strong focus has been put into the development of specialized computing architectures, able to leverage the sparsity of the computations to reduce the overall power consumption.

An attractive solution is represented by Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs), which provide exceptional flexibility over the fixed functionality of Application Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), allowing us to meet specific requirements, including custom encoding and signal processing tailored to the needs of SNNs. At the same time, the reconfigurable logic blocks of FPGAs can be exploited to implement control modules near the data-crunching logic which computes synapses and neuron dynamics, thus enabling to effectively take profit of sparsity by minimizing unnecessary computations and power consumption. This represents an advantage compared to microcontrollers, where sparse events are handled less efficiently due to their sequential instruction execution and condition checks. Finally, cost-effectiveness and accessibility justify the use of FPGAs over neuromorphic processors, which tend to be expensive and less accessible, although delivering high performance as being designed specifically for SNNs.

Based on these considerations, this work evaluates two SNN-based solutions for real-time sEMG processing on a specialized ultra-low-power accelerator implemented on the Lattice iCE40UP5k FPGA, targeting efficient human-machine interfaces on wearable devices. We start from a discrete gesture recognition problem, considering single finger gestures, and finally move to the more challenging continuous finger force modeling based on high-density (HD) sEMG. This also allows us to evaluate our specialized accelerator under a more pressing computational workload, where both the number of input channels and the sampling frequency of the data are significantly increased.

This work extends the preliminary study described in [8], where the SNN model was first assessed in gesture recognition performance on the NinaPro DB5 dataset. The main contributions of this paper are outlined in the following:

- we demonstrate low-power FPGAs and SNNs as useful instruments for wearable sEMG processing, achieving power/energy figures surpassing alternatives at the state of the art on a highly accessible technology;
- we present an SNN-based system for finger-gesture classification, improving the preliminary assessment presented in [8] by including the analysis of the performance achievable with single and double armband acquisition, reaching up to 83.17% classification accuracy;
- we consider the adaptation of the same network topology to the more complex task of continuous finger force

TABLE I
A COMPARATIVE SUMMARY OF RELEVANT WORKS IN GESTURE RECOGNITION BASED ON SEMG SIGNAL USING SPIKING NEURAL NETWORKS.

Work	On Hardware?	Dataset	Classes	Accuracy	Device	Energy per classification	Power during inference	Mops	Encoding
Our	✓	NinaPro DB5 ^A	12	83.17%	FPGA	44.58 μ J	11.31 mW	2.56	Delta
		NinaPro DB5 ^B		77.23%		37.45 μ J		2.15	
[3]	✓	NinaPro DB5 ^B	12	74%	Loihi	246 mJ	41 mW	11.56*	Delta
[4]	✓	custom 5 subjects	10	95%	Jetson	0.97 mJ	100 mW	7.97*	HD-sEMG Decomposition
[5]	✗	custom 8 subjects	8	97.4%	N.R. ^C	N.R.	N.R.	0.013*	Population
[6]	✗	custom 10 subjects	6	98.78%	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	6.57	Event- Differential
[7]	✓	custom 4 subjects	4	84.8%	SpiNNaker	N.R	1-4 W	N.R.	Delta

^A Double Armband.
^B Single Armband
^C Not Reported.
^{*} Estimated from the paper.

tracking, reaching up to 0.871 correlation compared to the direct measurements collected with force sensors placed on the fingers, with a single model applied to multiple patients in the dataset;

- we describe the upgrades developed for our specialized SNN accelerator from the original version presented in [9], to support efficient inference targeting both problems at hand;
- we extend the efficiency assessment conducted in [8], which demonstrated 3.94 ms and 44.58 μ J per single gesture classification on the Lattice FPGA, to the more demanding and compute-intensive force tracking task, where single inference requires 0.1 ms and 1.19 μ J, thus showing the best energy efficiency among the alternatives from the state of the art.

The article is organized as follows. Section II discusses related work, whereas Section III describes the datasets referenced for SNN performance assessment. In Section IV, we present the details of the encoding methodology, the considered SNN topology, and the target FPGA-based platform, whereas in Section V we report the performance assessment of the gesture recognition and force modeling tasks. Section VI reports the efficiency performance of the proposed implementations. Finally, Section VII discusses the direct comparison with the state of the art.

II. RELATED WORK

Movement classification from sEMG signal based on neural networks is well-documented in the literature. Relevant examples are represented by the works [10]–[12], presenting Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) or Temporal CNN (TCN) for hand gesture classification, reaching accuracy of over 93% on different reference datasets, with a focus on real-time low-power execution. Very promising results are also demonstrated by processing solutions relying on sensor fusion, such as in [13], where the sEMG signal is processed in combination with the electroencephalogram, and mechanomyogram.

Despite the remarkable results achieved with CNNs, we focus in this article on SNNs, considering the inherent efficiency of sparse computation. Therefore, in the following, we discuss recent works using SNNs for processing sEMG signals. We summarize key contributions in Table I, highlighting which studies consider wearable deployment as a design target, including on-hardware performance assessment. We also report the variety of gestures analyzed in terms of the number of classes, which can be regarded as a measure of the complexity of the problem addressed with the proposed solutions. The achieved performance is reported in terms of classification accuracy, as well as on-hardware efficiency. We finally include information about the computational complexity of the model, in terms of the number of required operations.

On-hardware performance assessment is included in most of the works proposing SNN-based processing [3], [4], [7]. Among these, we chose the seminal work conducted by [3] as our main reference point, as this study targets the open-source NinaPro database and considers the highest number of different gestures, specifically selecting a subset of DB5 that features 12 gestures. Their proposed optimal model achieves a classification accuracy of 74% using acquisition from a single armband. The efficiency of the model is demonstrated on Loihi [14], reporting 5.7 ms inference time, with 246 mJ energy per inference and 41 mW average power consumption for parallel execution on 12 cores. We compare with [3] using a lean topology with a reduced number of required operations, obtaining a similar accuracy on the same dataset, reaching 77.23%. We additionally assessed our system on the real-time processing of sEMG signal acquired by two Myo armbands, which improves classification accuracy to 83.17%. Nevertheless, executing our SNN on a custom ultra-low power SNN processor effectively exploiting sparsity, we significantly decreased power/energy consumption.

Hardware efficiency is also considered as a design objective in [4], proposing an SNN model applied to natural spiking information recorded from individual spinal motor neurons. In this case, the data processed to obtain the classification

is represented by HD-sEMG signals. The proposed solution reaches very high accuracy, up to 95%, although the complexity of the problem addressed is slightly lower, with only ten hand gestures considered. Nonetheless, the complexity of the model, in terms of the number of required operations, and the overall energy efficiency leave room for improvement, as an NVIDIA Jetson Nano was used as a target, providing 9.7 ms and 0.97 mJ per inference, and an average power consumption of 100 mW.

Similarly, the works of [6] and [5] obtained a remarkable gesture recognition accuracy, reaching over 97%, assessed on custom datasets. However, the reported accuracy results refer to an even lower number of gesture classes considered. Furthermore, direct measurements on target hardware are not provided, we thus report the number of the required accumulate operations for both models. As can be observed, the model in [5] represents a very lightweight workload, although it is important to note that the number reported in the table does not include the computations associated with feature extraction, performed with every inference run.

Finally, the work of [7] applies the NeuCube spiking model to the data from four volunteer subjects, achieving a classification accuracy of 84.8%. However, the proposed model is fairly complex, embedding 1471 neurons, and classification performance is evaluated on a reduced set of gestures, including only two-digit grasp, three-digit grasp, fist, and rest. Real-time classification assessment considered as a target the SpiNNaker platform [15], requiring a power consumption ranging from 1 to 4 W, thus significantly higher than the one we measured.

Moreover, as a significant new development, our study goes beyond gesture recognition and delves into the realm of real-time prosthesis control, tackling the more complex task of force modeling. We focus on the real-time decoding of the movement intention for every finger, by considering an HDsEMG dataset as a reference. We consider this problem as a more comprehensive approach to movement modeling based on sEMG processing. The works described up to this point focus on gesture recognition, with the exception of [7], which adapted the proposed classifier to also reproduce force distribution among the different fingers. The details of the assessment, performed on the custom dataset, are not reported, so we do not include this work among the direct references for force modeling. Other relevant examples exploiting non-SNN approaches are represented by the works of [16]–[19], addressing respectively classification of different force levels [16], continuous tracking of wrist angle during predefined wrist movements [17], and hand grip force estimation [18], [19].

Our work differs from the mentioned approaches since we aim to track the force of each individual finger during contraction and extension exercises, referring to the Hyser open-source dataset for performance assessment. Our main reference is provided by [20], which presents a deep forest model, applied to a set of features extracted from the HD-sEMG signal. The solution in [20] provides 0.952 average correlation to the direct measurements for each finger in one-day evaluation, with 0.866 R^2 . Cross-day force modeling was also addressed, reaching a correlation of up to 0.90 and 0.63

R^2 . Although targeting the same task and dataset, we consider in this work a very different approach, removing the feature extraction step and exploiting an SNN topology very similar to the one evaluated for the gesture recognition problem. More importantly, we consider the efficiency of our proposed solution, evaluating the power consumption of force regression performed on our target platform, which is crucial for ensuring the feasibility of real-time wearable hand prosthesis control.

A very recent relevant contribution to force modeling based on the Hyser dataset is represented by the work of [21], which presents an SNN-based regression approach to model finger forces deployed on a parallel microcontroller, with an energy consumption per inference of 6.5 μ J. Compared to their reported numbers, our FPGA-based implementation achieves a more efficient 1.19 μ J per inference. Finally, the work of [22] addresses finger force modeling on the same dataset, exploiting linear regression. In this case, hardware performance is not assessed.

Further discussion on the comparison with the main references ([3] and [20]–[22]) is detailed in Section VII. To the best of our knowledge, our proposed processing systems and implementations result in the most power-efficient solutions among the referenced SNN-based works for gesture recognition and force modeling tasks, while being fairly aligned with the state of the art in terms of accuracy.

III. REFERENCE DATASETS

We provide in the following a brief description of the datasets referenced for the assessment of our proposed processing system, namely the NinaPro DB5 for hand gesture recognition, and the Hyser dataset considered for the force modeling task. For both gesture classification and force modeling, the training set and the test set include the same group of subjects. As in most of the works in the literature, we do not focus on cross-patient modeling [21], [23]: for every new patient, some training data has to be acquired, usually by asking the patient to perform a few exercise repetitions, and a new training/refinement must be performed [24]. Such an effort of training a new network for a new subject is considered affordable, provided that the required number of samples is acquirable in a reasonable time.

A. Gesture recognition

The NinaPro DB5 dataset [25] collects sEMG and kinematic data recorded from 10 subjects, who did not have amputations or disabilities. Subjects were instructed to perform 52 distinct hand movements, following demonstrations shown on a laptop computer screen. The dataset is divided into several subgroups, each representing different types of gestures. Subgroup E1 consists of simpler gestures that involve single-finger movements, such as the flexion and extension of each individual finger, plus adduction and abduction of the thumb. This makes it a fundamental starting point for gesture recognition research. In contrast, subgroups E2 and E3 include more complex gestures, such as combined finger movements and interactions with objects. Considering [3] as our main reference in the

literature, we selected the same subset of 12 exercises collected in the E1 subgroup to align with the state-of-the-art.

The sEMG signals were recorded using two Thalmic Myo Armbands, with a sampling frequency of 200 Hz. Each subject's dataset includes recordings of six repetitions of each movement, with each gesture lasting about five seconds, followed by a three-second rest. This work presents the results of two gesture classification experiments: the first considers the acquisition of a single armband, to allow a direct comparison with our main reference [3]; the second involves the use of two armbands for signal acquisition, allowing us to increase the accuracy of the classification system.

Referring to the original naming reported in the dataset description, for our analysis we focused specifically on the sEMG data collected in the *emg* variable of the dataset, organized into 16 columns representing 16 acquisition channels. The first eight columns correspond to electrodes evenly distributed around the forearm at the height of the radio-humeral joint, while columns 9-16 represent the second Myo, tilted by 22.5 degrees clockwise with respect to the first armband.

We refer to the annotations reported in the *restimulus* variable for the labeling of the data, while we considered the repetition annotations reported in the *repetition* variable to split the dataset into training, validation, and testing subsets, as will be detailed in Section V-A.

B. Force Modeling

The Hyser (*High-density Surface Electromyogram Recordings or HDsEMG*) dataset [26], [27] represents a collection of data from 20 subjects, curated by Fudan University. It is organized into five sub-datasets, oriented towards 1) pattern recognition of 34 different hand gestures, 2) maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) of each individual finger, 3) one-degree-of-freedom contraction of individual fingers, 4) n-degree-of-freedom contraction of combinations of fingers, and 5) random exercises. All subsets, except the first one, also include force measurements collected with force sensors placed on individual fingers during motion execution.

In this work, we focused mainly on the third subset, considering force modeling based on HDsEMG signals during independent finger contraction and extension. Figure 1 reports an example of a force trajectory representing a single exercise: within a 25s time interval, the subjects performed a single finger contraction-extension exercise following a triangle-shaped force trajectory, reaching 30% MVC extension, 30% MVC contraction, and 30% MVC extension. The other fingers were relaxed during the exercise. Each subject repeated the exercise for each finger, performing three trials in two different sessions. The interval between the two sessions ranges from 3 to 25 days.

The sEMG data was recorded using 4 HD-sEMG electrode arrays placed on the forearm and a Quattrocento amplifier (OT Bioelettronica, Torino). The acquisition setup included 256 channels with 16-bit resolution, a low-pass filter with a cut-off at 500 Hz, and a sampling frequency of 2048 Hz. The force data were recorded at a 100 Hz sampling rate.

Fig. 1. Example of force traces available in the Hyser dataset. The plot refers to the typical triangular-shaped trace for thumb extension and contraction.

According to the Nyquist theorem, downsampling to 1000 Hz is sufficient to accurately represent the sEMG signal. Therefore, we filtered and downsampled the HD-sEMG signals to 1000 Hz. Similarly, we resampled the force reference measurements to 1000 Hz after filtering out frequencies above 10 Hz, as suggested in the reference papers presenting the dataset [20], [26].

In this work, we focused on one-day force modeling, considering data from the same recording session for training and testing. To enable a direct comparison with the previous work of [20], we focused on the data from session 2.

In line with the work of [20], the evaluation metrics considered are the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (*COR*), and the coefficient of determination (R^2), based on their standard definition reported in Equations 1 and 2.

$$COR = \frac{\sum (y - \bar{y})(\tilde{y} - \bar{\tilde{y}})}{\sqrt{\sum (y - \bar{y})^2} \sqrt{\sum (\tilde{y} - \bar{\tilde{y}})^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y - \tilde{y})^2}{\sum (y - \bar{y})^2} \quad (2)$$

Where y represents the ground truth of the measured forces, having mean value \bar{y} , and \tilde{y} is the output of the network model, having mean value $\bar{\tilde{y}}$.

IV. SNN MODEL FOR SEMG PROCESSING

In this section, we delineate the specifics of our proposed processing approach and discuss the encoding methodology adopted for spike generation, the data segmentation steps needed, the SNN models selected for gesture recognition and force modeling, and the custom FPGA-based inference engine.

A. Encoding

This research adopts Delta modulation, a well-known technique in signal processing and telecommunications, for digitizing analog signals. The mechanism of Delta modulation, described in Algorithm 1, yields two separate tracks, reflecting the signal's positive or negative deviation from a predetermined threshold. The encoding strategy we have implemented

Algorithm 1: sEMG Encoding with Delta Modulation

```

Input: sEMG signal
Result: Two signals of spikes per channel, POS and NEG.
1 delta sample = First sEMG sample;
2 delta value;
3 while sEMG signal do
4   for sEMG channel do
5     sEMG sample;
6     if sEMG sample > delta sample + delta value then
7       delta sample = sEMG sample;
8       POS_channel.append(spike);
9     else
10      POS_channel.append(no-spike);
11    if sEMG sample < delta sample - delta value then
12      delta sample = sEMG sample;
13      NEG_channel.append(spike);
14    else
15      NEG_channel.append(no-spike);

```

for finger gesture recognition differs from the traditional methods found in existing literature, as we utilize Delta modulation not just on the raw signal, but also on its first and second derivatives during processing. In the NinaPro DB5 dataset, the raw signals are stored as integers, thus, after extensive exploration and analysis, a delta value of 15 was chosen for the encoding algorithm in the gesture recognition task.

On the other hand, the Hyser dataset stores the raw HD-sEMG signals in floating-point format, we thus determined that a delta value of 0.033, expressed in fixed-point, would be optimal for the encoding. Despite the benefits observed in the gesture recognition task, we did not include the derivatives of the signal as input data for force modeling. The primary reason for this decision is the larger number of acquisition channels accessible in the HD-sEMG dataset (up to 256). Conversely, we also decreased the number of acquisition channels considered to 128, choosing only the data obtained by one of every two consecutive channels. Based on our results, this choice does not compromise the accuracy of the force modeling.

B. Segmentation

The segmentation procedure entails dividing continuous sEMG signals into discrete segments or windows, which are subsequently utilized to extract features and perform classification. We used different segmentation techniques in the two reference use cases.

For the classification task, we generate segment windows of 0.5 seconds, with a 0.1-second shift between consecutive windows. As the sampling rate is equal to 200 Hz, the time parameters are converted to sample-based values, resulting in a window size of 100 samples and a window stride of 20 samples.

In NinaPro DB5, samples are initially identified as *exercise* or *rest*. To uniformly label a group of samples within a window, specific rules have been established based on the distribution of labels per window. A window is defined as *exercise* when at least 80 percent of the contained samples are labeled this way. Conversely, it is classified as *rest* when all samples in the window carry the label *rest*. Windows that do

TABLE II
TOPOLOGY AND PARAMETERS OF THE PROPOSED SNN MODEL.

Layer	Synapse	Neuron
Dense Layer 1	<i>in</i>	64
Dense Layer 2	64	128
Dense Layer 3	128	64
Dense Layer 4	64	<i>out</i>

Gesture recognition (two-bands): *in* = 96, *out* = 13.
 Gesture recognition (single-band): *in* = 48, *out* = 13.
 Force tracking: *in* = 256, *out* = 5.

not meet these criteria are discarded from the training set. An initial delay of 2 seconds, translating to 400 samples according to the sampling frequency, was set to filter out the noise at the start of the signal before initiating the windowing process.

For the force modeling task, segmentation is not strictly required, as we decode the force signal continuously as soon as a new input sample is received. However, to partition the dataset for training, we have considered 25-second long windows, without overlap, to be used in the training, validation, or test set.

C. SNN topology and training

The network topology selected for our sEMG processing system embeds a sequence of four Dense layers, exploiting the Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) neuron model. Table II summarizes the parameters of the topologies exploited for the two use cases considered, distinguished by the number of input channels to be processed and of output variables to be computed.

The working principle of a single neuron is defined according to Equations 3, 4, and 5. Based on connections to previous layers of the network topology, each neuron receives a sequence of spikes s_{in} as input. Their contribution to the membrane voltage v of the neuron is weighted through the synaptic weight w of the corresponding connection. If a spiking threshold θ is reached, the neuron produces an output spike $s_{out}(t)$ and resets its membrane voltage; otherwise, the voltage gradually decreases over time, based on a decay factor α . In the following, we consider two alternative reset mechanisms to be applied once the threshold is reached or exceeded: *reset to 0* sets the voltage at the following time step to 0, whereas *reset subtract* subtracts the threshold from the previous value of the voltage, thus allowing it to preserve the residual difference.

$$\tilde{v}(t) = \alpha \cdot v(t) + \sum w \cdot s_{in}(t) \quad (3)$$

$$v(t+1) = \begin{cases} \tilde{v}(t), & \text{if } \tilde{v}(t) < \theta \\ 0, & \text{if } \tilde{v}(t) > \theta \text{ and reset to 0} \\ \tilde{v}(t) - \theta & \text{if } \tilde{v}(t) > \theta \text{ and reset subtract} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$s_{out}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \tilde{v}(t) \geq \theta \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

For each of the targeted tasks, we compared the implementation of the network topology based on two well-known frameworks for SNN training, namely SLAYER and SnnTorch.

Fig. 2. Overview of the sEMG processing system. The grey blocks represent units that are used exclusively for classification tasks and are not active during the force modeling process.

The results of the comparison are discussed in Section V. For gesture recognition, we leveraged the SLAYER framework [28] for the definition and training of the model, exploiting GPU-based training through the LAVA framework [29], [30]. The SLAYER implementation of the LIF neuron model enables tuning of the axonal delays, defining a different propagation time for the spikes along the axon. This feature was exploited in Dense Layers 1, 2, and 3, with a maximum delay value set at 62 time steps. For this classification task, we considered the decoding of the spike rate of the network output, computing the loss through the *slayer.loss* class, with a focus on *SpikeRate*-based calculations. We set a true rate target at 0.2 and a false rate at 0.03. The reset mechanism exploited in the LIF neuron is reset to 0.

On the other hand, for the force modeling task, we exploited the SnnTorch framework [31], which allowed us to train the decay of each neuron independently. The reset mechanism exploited in the LIF neuron is subtracting the threshold, and the spiking condition in Equation 5 is strictly $\tilde{v}(t) > \theta$. We selected the threshold value of the last layer of neurons to prevent the occurrence of output spikes and considered the membrane voltage of the output neuron as the output variable tracking the force traces. This approach is exploited in the literature for similar tasks, where SNN models are employed in regression problems [32], [33]. To this aim, we exploited the mean squared error as a loss function.

We exploited Google Colab for the training of our models, leveraging the computational power of T4 GPUs. We selected a batch size of 32 and exploited the Adam optimizer with an adaptive learning rate starting from a value of 0.0003, updated with a decay factor of 1/3 after 30 epochs with no improvements on the loss, for a maximum of 3 update iterations. We have shared the source code in an online repository to ensure reproducibility [34].

D. Target hardware platform

The efficiency of the proposed models was evaluated on a custom SNN processor [9], redesigned to match the limited resources of low-power FPGAs, such as the Lattice iCE40UP5k FPGA. A general overview of the processing system is represented in Figure 2.

A RISC-V processor oversees the data acquisition via the SPI interface and performs general control tasks. The system embeds an *encoding* stage, implementing the delta modulation

TABLE III
RESOURCE UTILIZATION OF THE FPGA FOR SEMG PROCESSING, SHOWING THE USAGE OF LOGIC CELLS (LC), DSP BLOCKS, BLOCK RAM (BRAM), AND SINGLE PORT RAM (SPRAM).

LC	DSP	BRAM	SPRAM
4262 (80%)	2 (25%)	27 (90%)	4 (100%)

algorithm described in Section IV-A, which produces the train of spikes to be processed with the SNN accelerator. As required for the gesture classification task, the system accommodates a *segmentation* block, assisting the creation of windows of data, according to the approach described in Section IV-B, and a *decoding* slot, which establishes the classification output by counting the spikes emitted by the neurons in the last network layer. The computing core is the *SNN Accelerator*, which is capable of executing real-time inference, by processing 8 synapses and 2 neurons per clock cycle, and hosting networks with up to 131,072 synaptic weights.

Table III shows the utilization of logic cells (LC), DSP blocks, BRAMs, and SPRAMs, providing a clear picture of the FPGA resource usage. In the following, we describe the implemented modules in detail.

a) *Encoding Slot*: In the classification task, 16 input channels are streamed in through the SPI interface every 5 ms. The first and second derivatives of the sEMG signal are computed through a dedicated LUT-based module, exploiting a BRAM to store the previous sEMG samples and first derivative values. Three delta modulator modules encode into spikes the variations in the signals, then the spike packet is stored in a BRAM-based rotational buffer counting 3 BRAMs, enough for storing 0.6 seconds of encoded input data, i.e. 120 samples. Finally, data segmentation is controlled by a counter, which streams 100 encoded samples to the SNN Accelerator, enabling gesture classification every 0.1 s. In the continuous motion decoding task, 128 input channels are streamed in through the SPI interface every millisecond. Since no derivatives computation is required in this case, the input encoded through delta-modulation is directly processed by the SNN accelerator.

b) *Multichannel delta-modulation hardware architecture*: The delta modulator architecture includes a single BRAM, used to store values for the *delta sample* (see Algorithm 1), two adders, and two comparators, exploited to monitor variations in the input signal.

c) *SNN Accelerator*: The *SNN Accelerator* integrates two *neuron modules*, implementing the LIF logic, that work in parallel, each computing the neuron dynamics for half of the neurons in the network. Specifically, the model is processed layer by layer, and the *neuron modules* integrate different neurons of the same layer concurrently. Each *neuron module* is capable of computing the contribution of four adjacent input synapses to the LIF input current, and then to the neuron voltage, at each cycle.

The synaptic weights are stored in independent dedicated weight memories, using 8-bit per synaptic weight. On the

TABLE IV
CONFIGURATION OF THE PROCESSING SYSTEM FOR THE TASKS ADDRESSED.

Task	Framework	Platform	Topology	Encoding	Neuron	Quant
Gesture recognition	SLAYER	Lattice iCE40UP5k	$in = 96, out = 13$	Delta encoding, derivative, segmentation	LIF with axonal delay, reset to 0	8 bit
Force Tracking	SnnTorch	Lattice iCE40UP5k	$in = 256, out = 5$	Delta encoding	LIF, reset subtract threshold	8 bit

TABLE V
CONFUSION MATRIX REPORTING FINGER GESTURE CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE ON NINAPro DB5 TEST SET, FOR 3-FOLDED CROSS-VALIDATION. NUMBERS IN BRACKETS ARE OBTAINED WITH A 200 MS TOLERANCE AROUND THE INTERFACE BETWEEN REST AND THE BEGINNING OF THE EXERCISE.

True Labels	Rest	40338 (40413)	221 (209)	66 (61)	77 (69)	79 (70)	123 (108)	25 (22)	101 (96)	20 (20)	18 (10)	206 (202)	29 (27)	56 (52)
	Index Flexion (Idx Flx)	701 (564)	1452 (1589)	112	113	78	42	51	80	37	12	20	9	14
Index Extension (Idx Ext)	290 (181)	220	1242 (1351)	28	51	13	26	15	3	3	8	22	11	
Middle Flexion (Mid Flx)	459 (350)	174	54	1526 (1635)	38	114	37	55	10	2	16	2	0	
Middle Extension (Mid Ext)	190 (95)	68	25	76	1374 (1469)	48	70	13	14	0	0	2	10	
Ring Flexion (Ring Flx)	259 (162)	15	31	123	62	1514 (1611)	27	87	27	0	4	7	3	
Ring Extension (Ring Ext)	255 (143)	62	10	63	90	95	1379 (1491)	170	43	6	0	10	16	
Little Flexion (Lit Flx)	517 (384)	74	20	53	39	46	200	1431 (1564)	70	7	0	7	18	
Little Extension (Lit Ext)	247 (126)	7	5	23	14	61	53	179	1481 (1602)	0	10	15	2	
Thumb Adduction (Thm Add)	279 (177)	27	3	12	0	5	3	9	22	943 (1045)	66	379	20	
Thumb Abduction (Thm Abd)	820 (656)	98	6	13	9	5	16	16	58	90	856 (1020)	119	74	
Thumb Flexion (Thm Flx)	178 (91)	23	9	3	7	10	15	15	18	281	25	1069 (1156)	54	
Thumb Extension (Thm Ext)	418 (289)	60	10	25	6	16	23	34	24	22	114	135	1052 (1181)	
	Rest	Idx Flx	Idx Ext	Mid Flx	Mid Ext	Ring Flx	Ring Ext	Lit Flx	Lit Ext	Thm Add	Thm Abd	Thm Flx	Thm Ext	

Predicted Labels

contrary, the input train of spikes is stored in a memory shared among the *neuron modules*, using 1-bit per spike. The memory address is computed dynamically, based on a control logic allowing the retrieval of the correct data for the execution of each layer. To take advantage of the event-based nature of the computing workload, a *spike stack* is combined with the address generation to keep track of the active synapses and skip over the inactive ones.

d) Axonal delay implementation: The *axonal delay* module enables the introduction of a customized post-synaptic delay, ranging from 0 to 62, for each neuron of the network. The hardware implementation consists of two BRAMs. The former is a FIFO with an entry of 62 bits per neuron, and the latter contains the neurons' axonal delay. Every time a neuron fires a spike, the spike is stored in the FIFO, in the location identified by the firing neuron ID and its axonal delay retrieved from the axonal delay memory. Then, when a neuron is integrated, its entry in the FIFO is shifted, the oldest spike is lost, and the just computed spike is shifted in.

e) Decoding Slot: The *decoding slot* is only needed for the sEMG classification task. Within the classification window,

the output spikes fired by the neurons representing each output class are received and accumulated. Finally, a comparator is employed to assess which neuron fired the highest number of spikes, and the associated class is selected as the classification outcome. In both use cases, the final computed output is then propagated through the UART interface.

f) Sparsity: The event-based nature of SNN processing is naturally efficient, as computations within the network are only performed at the occurrence of one event to be processed. Thus, throughout the network topology, neurons are only active when receiving an input spike, which represents the presence/absence of an event as a binary value. The efficiency gain resulting from event-based processing can be measured in terms of the percentage of inactive spikes compared to the maximum possible spike count, referred to as the sparsity of the model. To describe the extent to which the software sparsity can be translated into on-hardware efficiency gain, we defined a target-specific sparsity metric, which we called *sparsity-hw*. This new metric accounts for the parallelism enforced by our target platform, which processes groups of four adjacent spikes in parallel. The definition is reported in

Equation 6:

$$Sparsity-hw = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{j=1}^{G_i} g_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^L G_i} \right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where:

- L is the total number of layers in the network,
- G_i is the number of spike groups in the i -th layer,
- g_{ij} indicates whether there's at least one active spike in the j -th group in the i -th layer (1 if at least one spike is active, 0 otherwise).

TABLE VI

TEST CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE ON THE NINAPro DB5 DATASET, AVERAGE VALUES IN 3-FOLDED CROSS-VALIDATION.

Class	Recall	Precision	F1-score
Rest	97.53 %	89.74 %	93.47 %
Index Flexion	53.36 %	58.06 %	55.61 %
Index Extension	64.29 %	77.97 %	70.47 %
Middle Flexion	61.36 %	71.48 %	66.03 %
Middle Extension	72.7 %	74.39 %	73.53 %
Ring Flexion	70.13 %	72.37 %	71.23 %
Ring Extension	62.71 %	71.64 %	66.88 %
Little Flexion	57.66 %	64.9 %	61.06 %
Little Extension	70.62 %	81.06 %	75.48 %
Thumb Adduction	53.33 %	68.14 %	59.84 %
Thumb Abduction	39.27 %	64.60 %	48.84 %
Thumb Flexion	62.62 %	59.22 %	60.88 %
Thumb Extension	54.25 %	79.1 %	64.36 %
Accuracy tot	83.17 %		

TABLE VII

COMPARISON OF SLAYER AND SnnTorch TRAINING FRAMEWORKS FOR GESTURE CLASSIFICATION AND FINGER FORCE TRACKING TASKS.

Task	Metric	SLAYER	SnnTorch
Gesture recognition	Accuracy	82.4 %	83 %
	Sparsity	90 %	88 %
	Sparsity HW	77 %	64 %
Force Tracking	CC	0.577	0.889
	Sparsity	88.4 %	76 %
	Sparsity HW	65.96 %	43 %

V. SNN PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

We present in this section the assessment of the performance obtained on the finger gesture recognition and force modeling tasks with the SNN models described in Table II. To obtain the results reported in the following subsections, the processing system described in Section IV was adapted to each task, as summarized in Table IV. As reported in the last column of the table, the SNN model was quantized to enable efficient deployment on the designated hardware system and optimize memory usage, reducing the weight resolution to 8 bits and achieving negligible accuracy loss. With the aim of reducing the resources used on the accelerator, we utilized a 16-bit resolution, instead of 32-bit, to represent the internal voltage of each neuron and implemented a saturation mechanism to prevent overflow situations. The 16-bit saturation is not applied during training but is implemented only during inference. As we describe, this choice affects the two use cases under consideration differently.

A. Gesture Recognition task

The results reported in the following refer to two different approaches, where we considered sEMG acquisition from a single Thalmic Myo Armband, or from two armbands, exploiting all the data available in the dataset. As each Thalmic Myo Armband provides eight channels, the two approaches exploit different SNN models, distinguished by their input channel count.

The choice of restricting the acquisition setup to a single Myo device allowed us to align with our main reference, the work [3]. Due to this reason, for this first assessment, we assigned the first, fourth, and sixth repetitions to the training subset, the third repetition to validation, and the second and fifth repetitions to the testing subset, according to the test setup described in [3]. With this setup, we were able to achieve a classification accuracy of 76.51%. Nevertheless, we observed that a significant accuracy improvement can be obtained by increasing the amount of available data to include both Myo devices. With access to the data from both Armbands, the classification accuracy reached up to 82.42%.

The first row in Table VII summarizes the results of the preliminary assessment conducted for the selection of the training framework for the gesture recognition task. As can be observed, both frameworks reached comparable classification accuracy, however, SLAYER was preferred for providing a higher sparsity in the trained model.

Starting from the classification output resulting from the trained SNN models, we also applied a post-processing mechanism, discarding classifications that resulted in nonconsecutive labels, and restoring the last valid output classification. This voting mechanism allowed us to improve the accuracy of gesture recognition to 77.23%, for single-band acquisition, and to 83.1%, for two-band acquisition. Throughout the complete test dataset, there were no instances where the neuron voltage exceeded the saturation level within the 16-bit representation used to store the voltage values. Therefore, in this scenario, saturation does not lead to performance degradation in terms of accuracy.

At this point, we considered a more detailed assessment of the achievable classification performance, by performing 3-folded cross-validation. Thus we iteratively considered for testing repetitions 2 and 5, repetitions 4 and 6, and repetitions 1 and 3, obtaining non-overlapped test sets covering the whole dataset. The average accuracy for the 3-fold assessment is 83.17%. A detailed analysis of the classification performance across classes is shown in Table V, illustrating the cumulative confusion matrix. Table VI summarizes the recall, precision, and F1-score evaluated for each of the targeted classes. A recall value over 60% is observed for 8 out of the 13 classes considered. The worst performance is obtained on the recognition of index, little, and thumb flexion, and thumb adduction. Classification errors in finger gesture recognition systems often arise due to the inherent similarities between certain gestures and the involuntary movements that accompany specific actions. For instance, thumb adduction and thumb flexion are gestures that frequently result in misclassification. This is primarily because both gestures involve similar muscle

Fig. 3. Summary of the EMG signal classification across various repetitions for rest, and little finger extension gestures. The ground truth classifications are indicated in the background, while the results of the classification are marked as spots overlaid on the signal graph. Any discrepancies between the ground truth and the classification results are represented in black.

activation patterns. Finger movements are another source of classification errors due to the interconnected nature of finger muscles. For example, middle finger flexion often causes an involuntary extension of the little finger. This involuntary movement can confuse the recognition system, leading to the misclassification of the gesture.

The analysis of the confusion matrix highlights that a substantial portion of errors, approximately 50%, are concentrated in the matrix's first row and column, indicating a challenge in distinguishing the rest class from all other remaining gestures. Therefore, we assessed the effect of classification errors occurring at the rest-gesture interface, recognizing that the initial windows contain a mix of *rest* and *gesture* samples. Specifically, we implemented a 200 ms tolerance period around the onset of gestures, during which classifications of both the *rest* and the specific *gesture* classes were deemed acceptable. By introducing this tolerance, we attained an overall classification accuracy of 85.4%. The impact of the errors at the interface is highlighted in the confusion matrix, where we report in brackets the corresponding values after the 200 ms tolerance at the interface is applied. As can be observed, when considering the tolerance, the number of true predictions along the diagonal increases, while some of the errors along the first column and first row are corrected. The remaining most relevant errors result from the distinction between index flexion and extension, or between thumb adduction and flexion, as well as in the correct recognition of middle flexion from index flexion and ring flexion.

In Figure 3, we provide a graphical representation of the classification on the signal acquired during a period of example, including four repetitions of the little finger extension gesture, separated by a resting phase. The plot reports the classification output, placed according to the predicted class, based on the y-axis on the right. From Figure 3, it is evident that the misclassifications occur in isolated spots, suggesting that they can be effectively filtered using a voting mechanism. The figure is provided as a reference for real-time operation, nevertheless, it refers to a test including only repetitions 2 and 5, whereas repetitions 1, 4, and 6 were assigned to training, and repetition 3 to validation.

B. Force Modeling task

The results reported in the following refer to the one-day leave-one-repetition-out performance assessment. We leveraged a three-fold cross-validation approach to iteratively consider one of the three trials within the session as the test set. The performance of the force modeling was assessed by comparing the output produced by the network with the ground-truth force measurements provided in the dataset, considering average results on the three folds.

Considering the data available in the dataset, we trained a global model able to process the HDsEMG data of any patient and track the force of each finger during the considered movement. The second row in Table VII reports the comparison between the results achieved with different training frameworks. As can be noticed, models trained with SnnTorch reached a significantly higher accuracy in terms of cross-correlation with the measured forces, although the lower levels of sparsity enabled result in less efficient inference. As inference execution on the target hardware requires integer representation, we analyzed the dynamics of internal neuron voltages, noting saturation events occurring in the context of 16-bit data representation. This phenomenon leads to a drop in performance. Moreover, we assessed the performance of the same models with 6-bit weight resolution to determine whether reducing weight resolution would decrease saturation occurrences. In Table VIII, we present comprehensive results for all leave-one-out tests, including performance variations when applying weight quantization at 8-bit and 6-bit, demonstrating the trade-offs between computational efficiency and accuracy in quantized scenarios. The results in Table VIII also take into account the drop in performance due to saturation. As can be observed, 8-bit weight resolution yields better performance in almost all cases. Specifically, referring to the final test, the model having 8-bit integer weights has an average loss on performance metrics of 1%, and the model with 6-bit weights has a loss of 1.015%. Consequently, this version of the model was chosen as the best and is referenced in the following.

We obtained an average correlation COR of 0.875, with an R^2 value of 0.763, considering the comparison with the force measured for each finger during the exercise. As can be noted from a qualitative analysis of the output, the network

TABLE VIII
SUMMARY OF PEARSON CORRELATION COEFFICIENT (COR) AND COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION (R^2) FOR ALL FORCE MODELING TESTS IN THREE-FOLDED CROSS-VALIDATION WITH DIFFERENT WEIGHT RESOLUTION LEVELS. CROSS-VALIDATION CONSIDERED ONE-DAY INTRA-PATIENT ASSESSMENT, WITH ONE LEFT-OUT REPETITION AS THE TEST SET.

Data reference	Weight resolution	1st repetition test		2nd repetition test		3rd repetition test		Summary test	
		COR	R^2	COR	R^2	COR	R^2	COR	R^2
All fingers	Floating point 32 bit	0.8972	0.8018	0.8784	0.7710	0.8630	0.7406	0.8795	0.7712
	Integer 8 bit	0.8957	0.7987	0.8676	0.7515	0.8612	0.7392	0.8749	0.7631
	Integer 6 bit	0.8868	0.7849	0.8727	0.7607	0.8451	0.7141	0.8680	0.7533
Moving finger	Floating point 32 bit	0.9461	0.8938	0.9378	0.8733	0.9235	0.8502	0.9356	0.8725
	Integer 8 bit	0.9448	0.8917	0.9368	0.8709	0.9214	0.8449	0.9341	0.8692
	Integer 6 bit	0.9413	0.8816	0.9375	0.8607	0.9137	0.8240	0.9303	0.8555

Fig. 4. Qualitative comparison between the ground truth of finger force measurements and the network model output, for thumb extension and contraction monitored on patient 1.

model learns to track the force of the moving finger with sufficiently good accuracy, whereas the decoding of the force for the remaining fingers, not involved in the exercise, is not as accurate. As an example, we report in Figure 4 the comparison between the network output and the ground truth measurements for each finger during thumb extension and contraction for subject 1. As can be seen from the figure, errors are introduced on the generated signal compared to the ground truth signal even for fingers not directly involved in the selected exercise. On the contrary, there still remains a good match between the generated signal and ground truth on the movement of the finger directly involved during the exercise.

To quantify the impact of noise in reconstructing the forces of non-moving fingers, we also evaluated the accuracy of the force tracking when considering only the moving one, observing a significant improvement in the overall metrics, up to an average COR of 0.934 and an R^2 of 0.869.¹

VI. EFFICIENCY ASSESSMENT

In this section, we assess our on-hardware implementation of the previously described model. Subsection VI evaluates the sparsity registered during inference, whereas subsection VI-B discusses the measurements performed for the evaluation of real-time power consumption, and, finally, subsection VI-C discusses the latency of end-to-end sEMG processing.

¹These results exclude data from patient 20, which appears to be mislabeled in the dataset. It results in being an extreme outlier, while it aligns with other patients if the labels for the fingers *Index* and *Middle* are inverted.

A. Sparsity

We evaluated the inference sparsity for both the tasks targeted with the proposed SNN models, observing over 90% inactive spikes on average for the gesture recognition task, and 76% for the force modeling task. This metric was evaluated considering the average of active spikes when performing inference on the whole test dataset.

We evaluated the *sparsity-hw* available for both the problems considered, observing that up to 77.11% computation savings can be exploited on average in the gesture recognition task, and up to 43.3% in the force modeling task.

B. Power consumption

Our processing engine operates in different power modes. Table IX lists the power measured during the different modes.

We used a Digilent Analog Discovery 2 oscilloscope in conjunction with three shunt resistors of $3.3 \pm 0.033 \Omega$, installed across the three distinct power inputs on the Lattice iCE40UP5k FPGA, identified as V_{core} , $V_{CCIO0\&1}$, and V_{CCIO2} . The internal components of the FPGA receive a 1.2 V supply from V_{core} , while the I/O pins are powered by 3.3 V from the $V_{CCIO0\&1}$ and V_{CCIO2} circuits. The power consumed by the V_{CCIO2} circuit does not contribute to the calculation of power consumption since it is not used. Figure 5 shows the measurement setup, specifically representing the measurement of the V_{core} voltage. The SPI interface is used to connect to the oscilloscope for testing the device's external communication.

Fig. 5. Measurement setup, specifically representing the measurement of the V_{core} voltage of the Lattice iCE40UP5k FPGA. The SPI interface is also connected to the oscilloscope to test the device's external communication.

Fig. 6. Real-time measurement of power consumption for V_{core} in the gesture recognition case. From the graph, we can observe three distinct modalities: (1) Inference, (2) Idle, and (3) Acquisition and Encoding.

The first component can be measured when the accelerator is fully active. We also measured the average power consumption level for the data acquisition and encoding phases. Finally, when possible, the system switches to a power-saving state, e.g. to be used upon completion of an SNN iteration processing, until a new incoming data sample must be acquired. Table IX also reports the time spent in each state, when performing gesture recognition and force modeling.

Figure 6, shows an example of acquisition during gesture recognition and highlights the different execution phases.

TABLE IX
COMPARISON OF POWER CONSUMPTION ACROSS DIFFERENT TASKS.

Energy component	Power consumption		Time	
	V_{core}	V_{ccIO01}	Gesture	Force
Inference (P_{inf} , T_{inf})	10.37 mW	0.94 mW	3.94 ms	0.1 ms
Acquisition (P_{acq} , T_{acq})	6.91 mW	3.8 mW	0.28 ms	0.09 ms
Encoding (P_{enc} , T_{enc})	6.91 mW	0.94 mW	2.2 ms	0.12 ms
Idle (P_{idle} , T_{idle})	0.34 mW	0.94 mW	93.62 ms	0.69 ms

The time T_{inf} spent for inference of the SNN model depends on the sparsity. On average, on the gesture recognition dataset, T_{inf} is 3.94 ms. Therefore, the energy consumption per inference is 44.6 μ J. In the force modeling case, on average, T_{inf} is 0.1 ms. The corresponding energy consumption per inference is 1.19 μ J. Such energy contributions are reported in Table I.

Moreover, to account for all energy contributions over the entire interval between successive inference executions, and to highlight the benefits of dynamic power management, we use the figures reported in Table IX and Equation 7 to estimate the average power consumption. We consider the target inference execution rate for each task and the corresponding inter-execution period T : in the gesture recognition task, the target interval between consecutive classifications T is 100 ms, whereas, in the force tracking task, input spikes are acquired with 1000 Hz frequency, thus T corresponds to 1 ms.

$$P = \frac{(P_{inf}T_{inf}) + (P_{acq}T_{acq}) + (P_{enc}T_{enc}) + (P_{idle}T_{idle})}{T} \quad (7)$$

The average power consumption is 1.84 mW for the gesture recognition task and 3.69 mW for force modeling, where the difference between the two tasks depends on different sampling frequencies, number of input channels, and sparsity. As a result, the autonomy of the system can be estimated at 603 hours for the gesture recognition task, and 300 hours for the force modeling task, considering as a reference a 3.7V, 300 mAh battery supply.

C. Latency

This section discusses the latency of the system with regard to the time elapsed between data acquisition and processing, SNN model inference, and interpretation of results. Equation 8 provides a method to calculate the overall latency for both scenarios:

$$T_{latency} = (N - 1) \times (1/f_s) + T_{acq} + T_{enc} + T_{inf} + T_{vote} \quad (8)$$

where N is the number of samples in the acquisition window, which is 100 in the gesture classification task, and 1 in the force modeling task, and f_s is the sampling frequency; the contributions of T_{acq} , T_{enc} , and T_{inf} are in line with the definitions introduced in the previous subsection and whose values are reported in Table IX; finally, T_{vote} accounts for the time distance between two consequent windows considered for the post-processing of the gesture classification results through majority voting, which is of 100 ms (0 ms in the force modeling task).

Based on this simple model, the latency of gesture classification is estimated equal to 599.44 ms, whereas end-to-end force modeling requires 0.31 ms. If we consider the real-time operation of a monitoring device, the latency value provides a worst-case estimation of the gesture classification delay, as in practice, a class can be identified even if the corresponding gesture only occupies part of the acquired window. However, we also include an additional result obtained by decreasing the number of samples per window from 100 to 50. The improvement in the responsiveness of the system, with a latency

TABLE X
HDsEMG-BASED FINGER FORCE MODELING PERFORMANCE COMPARISON.

Model	All fingers			Moving finger		Time	Energy per inference	Power during inference
	MAE ^a	COR	R ²	COR	R ²			
[20] Bayesian	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	0.956	0.844	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
[20] Deep Forest	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	0.952	0.866	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
[22] Linear regression	N.R.	0.908	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
[21] Linear regression	(8.42 ±2.80) % MVC	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	0.07 ms	1.55 μJ	22.3 mW
This work, SNN	(9.39 ±1.02) % MVC	0.871 ^b	0.756 ^b	0.934 ^b	0.869 ^b	0.1 ms	1.19 μJ	11.31 mW

^a Cross-day assessment on the Random section of the dataset (subset number 5 in Section III-B).

^b Excluding subject 20.

reduced to 349.44 ms, would be traded with a reduction in accuracy to 81.37%.

In terms of throughput, the gesture classifications system performs 10 classifications per second, considering a time distance of 100 ms between consequent windows, whereas the force modeling system processes 1000 samples per second by operating on a continuous stream of sEMG data. This high throughput is essential for accurately tracking continuous finger movements and force, ensuring smooth and precise control in applications like prosthetics and advanced human-machine interfaces.

VII. DISCUSSION

In this section, we focus on the discussion of the results presented in Section V, evaluating the state-of-the-art context for the two main problems addressed.

A. Gesture recognition

The most relevant reference for the evaluation of our classification results is provided by the work of [3], which targets the same subset of the NinaPro DB5. Based on the description of the test setup provided by the authors, we were able to consider a direct comparison, showing an accuracy improvement of over 2% for gesture classification based on single armband acquisition. As highlighted in Section V-A, notably higher classification accuracy can be enabled by access to two acquisition devices, with a limited impact on the computational complexity of the model. In detail, our proposed SNN model requires the execution of 2.56 million of accumulate operations (MOPS) per classification, representing a more lightweight workload compared to the SNN proposed in [3], estimated to require 11.56 MOPS.

Regarding the efficiency of the classification, our custom FPGA-based implementation allows us to limit energy consumption per inference to 44.58 uJ in the worst case, which is around 6 times lower than the alternatives in the literature. For a fair comparison in terms of power consumption, we report the power measured during the most energy-intensive task, which is 11.31 mW measured during inference. This number stands out in terms of efficiency compared to the performance figures reported by other recent works, such as [7], reporting a range of 1-4 W per classification on the SpiNNaker platform, [3], reporting 41 mW per classification on Loihi, and [4], reporting 100 mW per classification on Jetson.

B. Force Modeling

In this work, we introduced significant improvements over our previous studies [8]. We addressed the increased computational workload of finger force modeling by re-evaluating our encoding scheme and removing the computation of derivatives, simplifying processing while maintaining accuracy. We chose the membrane voltage of the neurons in the last layer as the output variable, setting a high threshold to prevent spiking and allowing a wider range of values. We further enhanced the membrane voltage representation by implementing a reset mechanism that subtracts the threshold from the voltage instead of resetting it to zero. Regarding the hardware improvements, we optimized the architecture with pipelines and parallel processing to handle the increased load without compromising real-time performance. The improvements in the hardware architecture enabled a reduction of inference latency, essential for managing high sampling frequencies and numerous acquisition channels as required by HD-sEMG.

To the best of our knowledge, the only direct references for performance comparison regarding the force modeling task on the Hyser dataset are provided by the works of [20], [21], and [22]. The authors of [20] compare the performance of different modeling approaches, considering subject-specific models. The evaluated models are applied on a set of four features, namely root-mean-square, waveform length, slope-sign-change, and zero-crossing, computed on 40 continuous samples. We report in Table X the two solutions that demonstrate the best performance in one-day validation.

Considering that the algorithms described for comparison in [20] present a single output, and thus produce results related to fingers independently, we could estimate our approach to be fairly aligned in terms of accuracy, despite being tailored for energy-efficient applications. Based on the qualitative analysis of the shape of the reconstructed signal, such as the one reported in Figure 4, we consider the limited accuracy drop as an acceptable trade-off to regard our results as a baseline to enable wearable deployment. Furthermore, the results we obtained on the moving finger exceed those reported in the work of [22], which exploits the decomposition of the signal into the involved motor units prior to the linear regression performed for force estimation, without a clear focus on the efficiency of the approach for at-the-edge execution. The solutions in [20], [22] are not assessed in terms of power/energy efficiency, which leaves an open question on their suitability for real-time monitoring.

The only reference from the literature that provides a direct

comparison for the efficiency of our solution is the work of [21], presenting the implementation on a parallel micro-controller of an event-based linear regression, exploiting an encoding layer based on spiking neurons. The authors report a range of energy and power metrics, based on the sparsity of the computation. As can be observed from Table X, the flexibility of our FPGA-based implementation allows us more effective exploitation of the inherent SNN sparsity, resulting in a generally higher energy efficiency. In order to provide a comparison with their results, we performed the assessment of our model on the fifth subset of the Hyser dataset, including random movement of all fingers. Despite our approach not being specifically optimized for this more complex problem, the results we obtained are reasonably comparable to [21]. Our Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for each finger is $9.39 \pm 1.02\%$. In contrast, the referenced work reports an MAE of $8.42 \pm 2.80\%$. Although being slightly higher on average, our method exhibits a lower standard deviation, indicating more consistent and predictable performance. In both cases, the MAE is MVC-relative, as suggested in the dataset reference papers [26], [27].

VIII. CONCLUSION

This work introduced a low-power sEMG processing system, aiming to lay the basis for real-time prosthetic control. The proposed system leverages an SNN model, exploiting the natural efficiency of event-based computing for a low-power, edge-device-compatible solution. The performance of the system was assessed on two relevant problems involved in prosthetic control, such as discrete hand gesture recognition, based on the NinaPro DB5 dataset, and continuous finger force tracking, based on the Hyser dataset. The proposed system achieved a notable 83.17% classification accuracy, demonstrating the SNN's capability to distinguish twelve unique hand gestures from the NinaPro DB5 dataset. Furthermore, when evaluated in the finger force tracking task, the selected SNN topology resulted in a correlation of up to 0.875 with the force measurements collected in the dataset.

Optimized for the Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA, the architecture of the system excels in computational and energy efficiency. Despite its quantization aimed at minimizing memory use and boosting hardware efficiency, the model retained high accuracy, affirming its suitability for resource-constrained processing environments. The power consumption during inference is 11.31 mW. This demonstrates the system's power efficiency, which is further enhanced by dynamic power management during the entire execution. Specifically, the estimated average power is 1.84 mW for gesture recognition and 3.69 mW for force modeling. Consequently, this research provides robust groundwork for the development of an efficient sEMG-based real-time gesture recognition and modeling system targeting advanced human-machine interaction and prosthetic control.

Future work will focus on evaluating the system with entirely new users not included in the training set. This will enhance the repeatability and generalizability of our results. Moreover, we will also explore the application of our system

to a wider range of hand gestures, not limited to individual finger movements.

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